

HORIZON JU Research and Innovation Actions
HORIZON-EUROHPC-JU-2021-COE-01-01
European High-Performance Computing Joint Undertaking

Plasma Exascale-Performance Simulations CoE
101093261

D3.1
**Initial Report on MPI, Load Balancing and
Resilience in Plasma Codes**

WP3: Algorithms and Libraries for Extreme-Scale Plasma Simulations

Date of preparation (latest version): 31/12/2023
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DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Deliverable Number	D3.1
Deliverable Name	Initial Report on MPI, Load Balancing and Resilience in Plasma Codes
Due Date	31/12/2023
Deliverable lead	TUM
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Keywords	Performance Characteristics, MPI, Load balancing, Resilience and Communication Behaviour
WP/Task	WP3/Task D3.1
Nature	R
Dissemination Level	PU
Final Version Date	31/12/2023
Reviewed by	Pratibha Raghupati Hegde (KTH), Jennifer Faj (KTH) Måns I. Andersson (KTH) and Martin Karp (KTH)

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Partner	Date	Comment	Version
TUM	10/10/2023	First draft	0.1
TUM	07/12/2023	Final draft	0.2
KTH	08/12/2023	Final draft updated for internal review	0.3
TUM	20/12/2023	Revised draft after internal review	0.4
KTH	20/12/2023	Final cleanup for submission	1.0

Executive Summary

Efficient and reliable MPI communication is critical for the scalability, performance, and stability of applications, particularly in the context of scientific applications running on exascale computing. Understanding the issues and bottlenecks in communication is therefore critical to optimising the Plasma-PEPSC codes and to support their reach into exascale. This deliverable, D3.1, provides a first overview of the characteristics of the four Plasma-PEPSC codes: BIT1, GENE, PIConGPU and Vlasiator and then focuses on investigating and discussing strategies for mitigating communication overheads and optimizing their performance. With that it provides the basis for the further evaluation and helps the project focus on the particular key aspects of performance, select and/or extend the relevant tools to achieve a more detail analysis and to optimise the code. For this goal, the report provides an overview of communication characteristics, explores fine-grained CPU-GPU communication impact, discusses load balancing considerations, introduces performance analysis tools, examines resilience needs, and explores the integration of new MPI features. The document aims at describing the current state of communication in project codes, outline ongoing work on performance evaluations and tool development, and provide insights into upcoming MPI features that will enhance the performance, quality, and stability of the targeted codes.

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1 Introduction

Efficient and reliable communication is key to enabling scalability, performance as well as stability of applications. Especially when targeting exascale, communication overheads and optimizations come to a forefront and are therefore important targets in this project. This initial report summarizes the needed baselines, discusses initial experiments and provides target scenarios that help pave the way for the next steps in the project.

This deliverable is split into six sections:

- A brief overview of the communication characteristics of the four codes in the project, along with open questions, describing our path forward in the exploration of their performance optimizations.
- A summary of experiments studying the impact of fine grained CPU-GPU communication using a dedicated benchmark with a particular focus on interactions with MPI.
- Initial discussions of aspects of load balancing, which is typically the main reason for reduced scalability.
- Active and planned tool activities to support novel techniques of performance analysis and optimizations targeted at the codes in this projects, specifically extracting communication and topology information.
- A preliminary exploration of resilience needs and features for the codes in this project and how to explore the mapping of currently proposed MPI extensions to these codes.
- A short report on new features added to MPI 4.1 and planned for MPI 4.2 and MPI 5.0 and how they can contribute to the optimization of the target codes.

In summary, this document will describe the current state of the communication characteristics of the project codes, highlight current work on performance evaluations and tools completed in preparation of future optimization steps, and an outlook of new MPI features that can further enhance the performance, quality and stability of the Plasma-PEPSC targeted codes. It does, however, exclude topics that are not directly connected to communication or that are connected to properties of local algorithms.

2 Performance Characteristics of the Plasma-PEPSC Codes

The following section provides a short overview over the known or measured characteristics of the four codes in the project, together with open questions to be explored for D3.2.

2.1 BIT

BIT1 (Berkeley–Innsbruck–Tbilis) is an electrostatic Particle-in Cell (PIC) code optimized for plasma edge modelling and incorporating nonlinear plasma, neutral and impurity interactions via Direct Simulation Monte Carlo (DSMC) collision operators. Collision operators represent energy and momentum conserving binary collision models, simulating practically all possible elastic and inelastic collisions important for fusion-relevant plasma edge. Plasma-wall interactions (PWI) are modelled via energy and angular dependent particle sputtering models. Number of particle species is limited by available atomic and PWI data. At present more than thousand of atomic and PWI processes are implemented. Simulation geometry corresponds either to a plasma bounded by two walls (divertor plates), e.g. 1D SOL, or semi-bounded plasma used for plasma sheath modelling. The same is applied for BIT2 and BIT3 codes, representing 2D and 3D generalizations of the BIT1 code.

2.1.1 Communication Characteristics

BIT1 experiments revealed a detailed analysis of the communication pattern using Extrae/Paraver and IPM, enabling precise tracing of the communication dynamics and workload imbalance, respectively.

Experiments involve a strong scaling study of the two simulation scenarios. These are strong scaling tests as we fix the problem size and increase the number of cores in use, in this case up to 19,200 cores. The Ionization simulation stops scaling at 2,560 cores, e.g., the problem size per MPI process is too small, and the communication cost takes large part of the simulation time: for instance, for the run on 19,200 cores, the communication takes 57% of the total time with a large increase of the simulation. On 2,560 MPI processes, the relative parallel efficiency is 77% and 96% for the Ionization and Sheath test cases, respectively.

2.1.2 Open Questions to Explore

Optimizing the communication behavior in BIT1 requires both optimizing its halo-exchange pattern as well as identifying and optimizing load balancing. Avenues for this include the use of neighborhood collectives for neighbor exchange as well the use of new techniques for direct transfers from accelerators to improve communication performance.

2.2 GENE

GENE (Gyrokinetic Electromagnetic Numerical Experiment) is an open source plasma microturbulence code which can be used to efficiently compute gyroradius-scale fluctuations and the resulting transport coefficients in magnetized fusion/astrophysical plasmas. GENE is physically comprehensive, well benchmarked, portable, and highly scalable. GENE is freely available via webpage (<https://genecode.org>) and it is further developed by an international collaboration of physicists and computational scientists which is always open for new contributors. GENE has been used, among other things, to address both fundamental issues in plasma turbulence research and to perform comparisons with

tokamak and stellarator experiments. GENE is coupled to the geometry interface code GIST.

2.2.1 Communication Characteristics

Experiments show good parallelization behavior for GENE both for strong and weak scaling for a realistic case with the code version. It is therefore already possible to run GENE-3D on several 10,000 cores making above mentioned simulations with eight billion grid points possible at an expense of multiple 100,000 CPU hours. Focus will, therefore, be rather on improving individual message behavior (like message size reduction), rather than the general overall pattern.

2.2.2 Open Questions to Explore

Previous work exposed three main areas to focus on when optimizing GENE: a) enhancing the needed fine-grained communication between CPUs and GPUs when porting to heterogeneous architectures; b) using compression to reduce the impact of the large messages (which is handled by a separate project funded by the German BMBF); and c) use of modern communication primitives available in the latest MPI standard.

2.3 PIConGPU

PIConGPU (Particle in Cell on GPUs) is a fully relativistic, manycore, 3D3V particle-in-cell (PIC) code. The Particle-in-Cell algorithm is a central tool in plasma physics. It describes the dynamics of a plasma by computing the motion of electrons and ions in the plasma based on Maxwell's equations.

In PIConGPU, electromagnetic fields are stored and advanced on a cartesian grid in space, whose nodes are edges of cells. This is a result of advancing the fields in time by solving Maxwell's equations with a finite-difference time-domain method, i. e. a stencil based approach.

Macro-particles move freely within the simulation volume, but the distance they can cover within one time step is limited to less than one cell, since cell size and time step are related by the Courant-Friedrich-Lewy condition in particle-in-cell simulations which ensures numerical stability by limiting the distance any signal can travel within one time step to less than one cell.

2.3.1 Communication Characteristics

The high-level communication structure for PIConGUP is shown in Figure 2.3.1. For each subvolume, field and macro-particle dynamics are advanced for one time step in parallel to the others. The advanced field values on the grid and particles leaving the subvolume are exchanged with the neighboring subvolumes. Due to solving field equations with a stencil method and the limit of macro-particle propagation distance to less than one cell, there is only next-neighbor communication of fields and particles in PIConGPU. That is, each MPI rank communicates boundary regions of its subdomain to the respective neighbor and stores the neighbor's boundary region into its guard region

Figure 1: PICongGPU data flow provided via the PMacc library across local super cell domains. In general, both core and border are exposed to physics algorithms such as field solvers, while the guard (ghost) is not exposed and takes care of caching data for communication. Due to the task parallel design of the PMacc library with data transfer across the memory hierarchies in a heterogeneous compute environment and the implementation of data dependencies between kernels latencies due to communication are effectively hidden and any task can be executed once all input data is available.

by asynchronous point-to-point communication.

PICongGPU implements data parallelism via the alpaka library [1, 2] and in addition adds task parallelism via the library PMacc, which functions as a middle layer between the physics code and the cross-platform parallelization library alpaka. The PMacc library implements all generic data types, communication and parallelization constructs, providing a generic particle-mesh library interface to implement the physics algorithms in PICongGPU.

Its main data constructs are the super cell and the particle attribute tile, both tiled data structures that provide a fully local domain for physics kernel development, while communication across local domains is provided by PMacc. Conversion of PMacc data types to MPI data types is provided by PMacc and is typically not exposed to the user side.

Communication is fully task-parallelized, with both compute kernels and communication kernels written in alpaka executing concurrently in a non-blocking way, see Figure 2.3.1. This includes intra-node communication, e.g. between GPU and CPU as well as inter-node communication via MPI.

Thus, all communication latency can be easily hidden. Data exchange of various field

entities such as electric and magnetic fields or currents as well as particle data can be executed independent of each other and independent for all directions in the cartesian mesh. This allows for fine-granular overlapping of communication and compute. In particular, we have implemented data-dependencies between all PIconGPU kernels via PMacc that allow to decide what data each kernel needs as input and provides as output. This information allows for task scheduling once all relevant input data is available and non-blocking communication of output data for all kernels within PIconGPU.

As alpaka provides a common, platform-agnostic abstraction towards task parallelism, this works out of the box for PIconGPU for all alpaka backends and thus on GPU hardware by NVIDIA, AMD, Intel as well as x86, ARM and RISC-V based systems, using one of the following alpaka backends, CUDA, HIP/ROCm, SYCL, OpenMP, or oneTBB. If available, GPU aware MPI can be activated by the user via a commandline parameter (see also Deliverable D5.1).

The PIconGPU domain decomposition is currently Cartesian and employs the `MPI_Cart` communicator for cartesian coordinates. Load balancing is currently static. For in-memory workflows and code coupling via the openPMD library we have operated coupling between PIconGPU as a data producer and other codes for data consumption using the ADIOS2 backend of openPMD operating both within a single MPI context or using separate MPI contexts. RDMA is supported by libfabric.

In parallel to the central particle-in-cell algorithm PMacc provides a plugin mechanism that allows to compute derived data for analysis from the particle and cell data. Some plugins make use of an allreduce that uses collective MPI reduction, e.g. when computing the plasma phase space density across the whole simulation domain.

2.3.2 Open Questions to Explore

Resilience and one-sided communication are open topics that we would like to explore further. An even more pressing issue is advanced support for complex coupled in-memory workflows. We will closely analyze the benefits of future versions of the MPI standard to critically evaluate new constructs for increasing communication throughput and simplification of communication in heterogeneous systems. The clear separation of concerns provided by the PMacc library enables us to quickly adapt to new technologies with minimum changes on the user side implementation of physics algorithms.

2.4 Vlasiator

In Vlasiator, the world's first global Eulerian hybrid-Vlasov simulation code, ions are represented as velocity distribution functions, while electrons are magnetohydrodynamic fluid, enabling a self-consistent global plasma simulation that can describe multi-temperature plasmas to resolve non-MHD processes that currently cannot be self-consistently described by the existing global space weather simulations. The novelty is that by modelling ions as velocity distribution functions the outcome will be numerically noiseless.

Due to the multi-dimensional approach at ion scales, Vlasiator's computational challenges are immense with relatively large messages used in MPI communication [3]. We

use advanced high performance computing techniques to allow massively parallel computations on tens of thousands of cores.

2.4.1 Communication Characteristics

Vlasiator makes heavy use of composite MPI datatypes, representing its sparse mesh datastructure in indexed datatypes that are dynamically created and destroyed for each simulation cell at each timestep. These datatypes are used both for neighbor communication inside the physical solvers, and I/O serialization into VLSV output files using MPI-IO.

These individual, per-cell indexed datatypes are further collated into derived array datatypes by the DCCRG grid library [4], to reduce communication between MPI task to one message per communication partner.

2.4.2 Open Questions to Explore

The extended use of datatypes, while very beneficial for code clarity and maintainability, may have some performance implications that should and will be pursued. This could lead to both advances in the code as well as feedback back to the MPI implementors. This is especially interesting in the combination with neighbor communication, as used here.

3 Investigation of Fine-Grained CPU/GPU Communication Plus MPI

One of the key bottlenecks in today's systems are the needed fine-grained communication between CPU and GPU. For this, many approaches have been proposed and successfully implemented. However, often overlooked is the interplay — and often interference — between this communication and cross-node communication using MPI.

Device synchronizations are enabled by device vendor APIs, e.g., `cudaDeviceSynchronize` in CUDA. These functions enable coarse-grained synchronization at GPU kernel boundaries, serializing the execution of CPU and GPU code by blocking the CPU execution until the GPU kernel is finished. Such CPU/GPU synchronization can lead to overhead in the form of idle CPU time due to the blocking synchronization, kernel termination times, and serialization of the GPU and CPU tasks at the granularity of kernel boundaries.

As the GPU/CPU control synchronization leads to unavoidable overheads, there have been significant efforts to remove the GPUs' dependency on CPUs and with that limiting the needed synchronization. Some of these efforts are GPU-Direct for communication, Unified Virtual Memory (UVM) for memory synchronization, and Cooperative Groups for enabling Multi-GPU synchronizations. However, all of these improvements come with their own overheads and/or require additional hardware not available on many systems. This is not expected to change in the future, and, consequently, we need to, even in these scenarios, find solutions that enable fine-grained CPU/GPU communication.

In order to overcome this challenge, we design and implement a novel, yet simple pinned host memory based notification mechanism that enables finer granularity non-blocking communication between the CPU and the GPU without altering control

flow. We showcase the performance advantages of our notification approach on the halo-exchange communication pattern using CPU triggered MPI communication. We demonstrate how enabling persistent kernels—to avoid multiple kernel launches together with reducing CPU idle time—and overlapping MPI with GPU operations improves overall performance, which more than compensates the small overhead introduced by the notification mechanism. With this use case, we also demonstrate how execution on the GPU affects the performance of concurrent MPI communication orchestrated by the CPU.

On average kernel launch and termination overhead can add up as high as 20 μ sec [5], according to our initial measurements on different systems one time round trip notification overhead between CPU and GPU is in the worst case comparable to kernel launch time or in the best case in nanoseconds range. Considering the aim of overlapping most of the notifications with other pack, unpack and MPI operations on CPU and GPU, our new approach is expected to offer performance gain in range of 20 μ sec in the best case. Considering the iterative nature of the scientific computation codes, the offered gain will grow with the number of iterations in the code.

We experiment with our approach on a micro-kernel before attempting the application on our larger applications. In particular, we use the Comb benchmark developed at LLNL, which is an extensive and complex benchmark with many parameters and measurement capabilities. Our results, which are also validated with a matching performance model, show the sources for performance overheads and ways to eliminate them, including fine grain task hand-overs, avoiding bus contention and fusing kernels. Detailed results are available in Bengisu Elis et al. [6]. The next step will be to apply the same optimizations to the Plasma-PEPSC codes.

As a result of our initial experiments we observed that on some of the systems our notification system causes overheads in MPI operations and read accesses on the CPU. Our initial investigations showed that this overhead in CPU operations can be reduced or removed by padding the message buffers. We will continue to investigate the source of the overhead in CPU operations and how to mitigate as a future work. In addition by using the K-model in [7] we established a baseline for our mechanism. Comparing our initial results, significant gap between the model prediction and our measurements is observed. Investigation of the gap between the performance model and our experiments is another future work in our agenda.

4 Initial Assessment of Load Balancing

4.1 BIT

During the initial assessment of BIT1 code performance, a study of load balancing was conducted to trace its communication patterns precisely. Fig. 2 shows a communication phase in BIT1. It can be noted that the MPI communication is non-blocking point-to-point (`MPI_Isend` / `MPI_Irecv`) and only involves neighbouring processes (this is halo exchange in a one-dimensional domain-decomposition). The important point is that the MPI process with rank 0 starts the communication late, e.g., it has more computation than other processes or is slower. Faster neighbour processes (MPI processes with ranks 1 and 7) must wait for the MPI process with rank 0 to proceed. A simple tracing reveals that there is a potential imbalance situation. In particular, the trace of the parallel BIT1

Figure 2: The MPI communication pattern is obtained, using `Extrae/Paraver`, with BIT1 using eight MPI processes on Dardel. The trace shows that MPI communication is non-blocking point-to-point and only involves neighboring processes. The MPI Rank 0 is the slowest. MPI processes with ranks 1 and 7 wait for it, leading to a load imbalance.

communication shows the rise of workload imbalance, with the MPI process with rank 0 being the slowest and other neighboring MPI processes waiting for it as they are locally synchronized by the `MPI.Wait` call.

Figure 3: MPI aggregated communication time for the BIT1 Sheath simulation on 19,200 cores. The insert shows the usage of memory per compute node.

As suspected by the previous analysis, in the largest simulation conducted in the strong scaling test: 19,200 MPI processes on 150 nodes, using the Sheath test case.

Fig. 3 shows that the MPI processes at the domain boundaries (MPI processes with Ranks 0 and 19199) take more than double the time in MPI procedures. The MPI time is dominated by the `MPI_Wait` synchronization function, showcasing a problem with load imbalance, as we have stated before. In addition, we observe that, excluding the boundary MPI processes, there are three large groups of MPI processes, which are self-synchronized: two groups have an aggregated MPI call time of approximately 20 seconds, while one group has an aggregated MPI call time of approximately 10 seconds. The self-synchronization is due to the presence of idle waves in a memory-bound MPI application with a simple communication pattern. This is also directly related to memory usage, where we observe that part of the computing nodes has a more considerable use of the nodes, approximately 23% more: the largest usage of memory per node is approximately 34 GB while the smallest is approximately 26 GB.

More details are published by Jeremy J. Williams et al. [8].

4.2 PIConGPU

Load balancing is static in PIConGPU. The user can explicitly configure the distribution of compute devices over the Cartesian domain decomposition via a commandline parameter. This allows to distribute compute resources evenly across the simulation volume by assigning regions of higher macro-particle density to more compute devices.

4.3 Vlasiator

Vlasiator’s sparse velocity grid structure [9] scales the velocity mesh complexity and with it the computational effort of each simulation cell in accordance with the velocity space coverage above a chosen phase space density. Computational weight of a simulation cell is thus roughly proportional to its plasma temperature times density, plus potentially strong effects of nonthermal kinetic effects. Figure 4 shows an example map of the load balancing metric for a production-scale simulation of Earth’s magnetosphere.

Since Vlasiator’s scientific target domain, simulations of Earth’s whole magnetosphere, encompasses density and temperature contrasts of up to two orders of magnitude, massively inhomogeneous computational load is generated. Already in early stages of Vlasiator’s development [10], it was therefore decided that a versatile and efficient load balancing mechanism would be required to enable scaling of the simulation system to the desired scientific target case. Vlasiator’s grid library, DCCRG [4], allows dynamic rebalancing of the simulation with arbitrary spatial partition on a cell-by-cell basis. Partitioning decisions are delegated to the Zoltan library [11], which provides a versatile set of partitioning algorithms. In production runs, Vlasiator has primarily been run with Recursive Coordinate Bisection (RCB) and Recursive Inertial Bisection (RIB) partitioning approaches, with the optimal choice being determined empirically on a case-by-case basis.

Re-evaluation of the load balancing state, and redistribution of simulation load happens dynamically at runtime, at simulation timestep intervals specified by the user in the run config file (in production runs, an interval of 50 simulation steps between load balancing is common). Further, load balancing can be triggered manually at run time by the user by creating an empty file named `DOLB` in the run directory.

Figure 4: A typical Vlasov magnetospheric simulation has a high contrast in computational complexity for different spatial cells. The *velocity space block count* shown here quantifies the approximate numerical effort for solution of the Vlasov equation in each simulation cell. Two orders of magnitude of contrast exist between the cheapest (magnetotail lobes) and most expensive (inner magnetosphere near the polar cusps) cells.

Figure 5: Exemplary plots of the spatial MPI domain decomposition in Vlasiator magnetosphere simulations. The figures show a polar-plane cut through the 3D simulation volume with Earth in the centre, coloured by individual MPI rank domains. The black and gray contour lines mark mesh refinement interfaces, consecutively refining from coarse cells in the outer simulation domain to fine cells in the inner magnetosphere. The four panels show partitioning based on Zoltan’s *Recursive Coordinate Bisection* (RCB, top left), *Recursive Inertial Bisection* (RIB, top right), Hypergraph (bottom left) and hierarchical partitioning (bottom right).

5 Performance Tools to Support Communication Assessments

In order to measure, analyze and optimize performance aspects of the Plasma-PEPSC codes, the usage of tools is essential. In addition to existing state-of-the-art performance tools, like mpiP, HPCToolkit, Vampir, Scalasca, Extrae/Paraver, IPM and TAU, which provide a core understanding of the performance characteristics of our codes, we also rely on new developments developed in other projects and apply and adapt them to the codes in this project. The following section briefly discusses the tools and the needed adaptations.

5.1 QMPI

While MPI provides comprehensive tool support in the form of the MPI Profiling interface, PMPI [12], which has inspired a generation of tools (including many of the tools mentioned above), it is not sufficient for the new arising challenges. In particular, it does not support modern software design principles nor the composition of multiple monitoring solutions from multiple agents or sources. For this, we are currently developing *QMPI* [6] in close collaboration with the tools working group in the MPI Forum, as a possible successor to PMPI.

As its central concept, it eliminates the fixed name shift interface and replaces it with a dynamic name shift mechanism that tools can query to identify a function pointer for the corresponding MPI functionality. This allows the use of an arbitrary number of name shift indirections and essentially enables a direct linking of multiple tools between an MPI call in the application and the actual execution inside the MPI library. The result is a dynamically configurable tool stack. With this concept, multiple software components relying on MPI interception, such as user tools, runtime tuners or system monitoring agents, can work alongside each other without interference, without even knowing each other.

We will use our prototype implementation and deploy it for our Plasma-PEPSC codes to a) dynamically insert performance tools, b) concurrently run multiple tools and retrieve consistent results, c) achieve custom tool behavior by composing multiple tools, and d) adding targeted code specific tools and analysis methods.

5.2 Generic Library Wrapping

The QMPI approach is not specific to MPI, but can be applied to any library with a well-defined interface. We are therefore currently extending the QMPI to support arbitrary libraries by providing a mechanism to auto-generate stackable library interceptors for a given header file. We have experimented with this technology on several numerical libraries, enabling us to track the usage behavior of applications on that library, as well as correlate the behavior of multiple libraries. In particular, we are studying the memory allocation and usage behavior.

We are currently extending and hardening this approach to track libraries in the Plasma-PEPSC codes, starting with the GENE code. Also here, our focus is on memory allocation and usage, in particular with respect to usage of different memory kinds, like

NIC, GPU or CPU, we are expecting that this will give us deep insights into the code behavior as well as potential optimization opportunities. This tool is in its early stage and will be ready to use in the next months.

5.3 Sys-Sage

HPC systems are getting ever more powerful, but this comes at the price of increasing system complexity. In order to use HPC systems efficiently, one has to be aware of their architectural details, in particular details of their hardware topology, which is increasingly affected by dynamic runtime settings. The same is true for all Plasma-PEPSC codes, which rely on a correct mapping of codes to hardware. This is even more important on systems with heterogeneous and/or accelerated nodes, as it is the case for all current EuroHPC systems.

sys-sage [13] is a novel approach providing an infrastructure for storage, correlation, and provision of HW-related system information, including topology data. It uses information from various well-known sources as well as use-case-specific solutions, and correlates the particular pieces together to provide a full view of a system. The data can then be used by tools, optimizers as well as applications themselves to understand the hardware they are running on, track changes in the hardware configuration, track transient behavior and to use it for optimizations.

The properties of an HPC system are represented in *sys-sage* in the form of *Components* and *Data Paths*, which are interlinked with each other, providing a correlation of the different information.

Components have a hierarchical tree structure, providing a structure that is easy to understand for the user, and is easy to navigate in. It forms the core of *sys-sage* and all additional information (static and dynamic) is connected to and referenced from it.

Each *Component* is of a certain *Component Type* — a class derived from different parts of computer systems so that their specific attributes and functionalities can be represented. Example *Component Types* are **Node**, **Storage**, **Memory**, **Chip**, **Cache** or **Core**.

A *Data Path* is a construct that carries information about the relation of two arbitrary *Components*. Each *Data Path* has a source and a target *Component*. Apart from that, no other rules apply — any information can be stored by a *Data Path*. It is up to the user to define how *Data Path* are built and what information they carry.

sys-sage is publicly available, and can be used by many applications. It integrates widely used approaches, such as hwloc or dynamic counter information, and offers user-integration of all other user-specific data sources. We use this option to add code and platform specific measurement source, in particular to support GPU-based platforms. Initial experiments to automatically determine, track and report the properties of the cache hierarchy in a vendor independent way are promising and will be critical for this project.

6 Resilience Requirements and Assessment

All the four Plasma-PEPSC codes support a basic fault-tolerance mechanics based on checkpointing and restart capabilities: this requires to save all the required information

cyclically, e.g. at given simulation cycles, to storage using parallel I/O and in case of restart perform a parallel read operation to initialize the simulation with the data from the last checkpointing data. Both BIT1 and GENE feature custom checkpointing and restart capabilities while Vlasiator uses the `VLSV library`, based on parallel MPI-IO.

Regarding PIconGPU, from our experience, the main issue arising during operation of large scale HPC systems are node failures. PIconGPU tackles this by allowing the user to write checkpoints of the full simulations state in arbitrarily set intervals. Times of checkpoint writing can be set in terms of simulation time step intervals, at a specific simulation time steps, in terms of elapsed wall time, and on occurrence of batch system signals. The latter can be send to the simulation by the batch system itself as a result of an unexpected event, or by the user while the simulation is running, or pre-configured in the batch-job script to be send at a specific time. This capability also allows to use PIconGPU as backfilling jobs in interruptible batch system queues. PIconGPU can resume the simulation from these checkpoints after restart of the job, usually on a different set of nodes.

Checkpointing and restart are basic mechanisms for fault tolerance and in the project, we aim at investigating new proposal and strategies to support resilience, e.g. the application continue its execution and deliver correct results despite the occurrence of failures. Resilience in applications require MPI support for error detection at runtime and possibility of shrinking/expanding communicators and efficient dynamic process management. We review three MPI proposals that impact the possibility of developing resilient MPI applications, such as the ones in Plasma-PEPSC.

6.1 User Level Failure Mitigation

The User Level Failure Mitigation (ULFM) interface, developed by the Fault Tolerance Working Group within the MPI Forum, is proposed to support MPI applications recover from MPI process failures [14, 15]. In summary, ULFM provides mechanisms for detecting process failures, recovering from failures by redistributing tasks via the dynamic creation of MPI processes to replace failed ones within an MPI application. More specifically, ULFM focuses on fail-stop process failures and supports strategies for application-level failure detection, via error codes for instance. It also provides failure mitigation mechanisms based on removing failed processes by shrinking communicators.

6.2 MPI ReInit-based Recovery

MPI ReInit has been introduced to supporting an easy global-restart recovery mechanism [16]. ReInit is a proposed MPI extension with a function call that sets a rollback point in the application. The strength of the MPI ReInit strategy is that it transparently supports MPI recovery, by spawning new MPI processes and changing the MPI World communicator at runtime. In summary, ReInit provides an initial MPI state akin to the state after MPI initialization. The weakness of this approach is that the existing implementation of ReInit is hard to deploy, since it requires integration with the job scheduler.

6.3 The Role of MPI Sessions in Resilience

An important new MPI feature is the concept of MPI session that provides the concept of isolation into MPI [17]. This requires relaxing the requirements for global initialization, which currently produces a global communicator, MPI Comm World. Instead, each MPI Session provides its own isolated MPI environment, with the possibility of having different settings, optimization opportunities, and communication data structures. When it comes to resilience, MPI Sessions strategically can enable dynamic resource allocation leveraging the Process Management Interface for Exascale (PMIx) that can be used by job schedulers such as SLURM.

7 Advances in the MPI Standard

The MPI forum is continuously advancing the MPI standard to better suit the community as well as codes like the ones discussed here. However, only when adjusting the codes to take advantage of these new features, we can really benefit from many developments. The following discusses several planned or recently added features, that we have or will investigate for usage in the Plasma-PEPSC codes. Note, resilience is omitted here, as it in some areas goes beyond MPI and into OS services, and is also already covered in Section 6.

7.1 MPI Sessions for Malleability

As described previously when discussing resilience in applications, one of the core features added in MPI 4.0 and slightly refined in MPI 4.1 is the concept of MPI Sessions, which introduces a new way to initialize MPI, enables partial initializations to improve startup scalability, provides a path to malleability, and supports hardware specific mappings to node groups. We are tracking this feature to see how it can be applied to improve library modularity or startup performance. However, current implementations are mostly dummy wrappers, negating possible performance improvements, and, hence, we need improved library implementations before this feature will impact performance.

7.2 Memory Kinds

MPI 4.1 has introduced so called memory kinds, the ability for MPI to distinguish and specifically support memories allocated for different devices and by different handlers. We will gradually work this feature into the Plasma-PEPSC codes, as the feature becomes available in the MPI distributions. This will enable faster communication as well as the direct support in MPI for GPU-GPU communication.

This feature is enabled via an Info object available as part of the Sessions Interface, requiring us to replace initialization with sessions before adding the support for memory kinds. With that, the application (or library) can query the available support and introduce fast code paths to support efficient accelerator communication.

7.3 Persistent and Partitioned Communication and Collectives

The MPI Forum has recently added and still is adding new communication modes. N3w features are to enable persistent collectives, i.e., the ability to specify parameters for a collective once and then repeatedly simply invoking this collective, or the support for automatic buffering. Further, new additions for persistent operations as well as partitioned communication. We will provide use cases from the Plasma-PEPSC codes to the forum to support the inclusion of fitting operations, as well as deploy the new operations as soon as libraries include support.

7.4 Option for an MPI ABI

The final feature to watch is the current development of an MPI ABI (Application Binary Interface), which is tentatively targeted for MPI 4.2 in the near future. We will use the codes in this project as a test case for this work to ensure the developed solution works for our codes. The effect of the ABI will be an easier deployment, including in virtualized cloud environments, as well as the dynamic substitution of MPI libraries without recompilation.

8 Conclusion

This deliverable, D3.1, provided an overview of the current state of communication characteristics, fault-tolerance mechanisms, and opportunities for using new MPI features, within the Plasma-PEPSC codes. The analysis of CPU-GPU communication impact, load balancing considerations, and the introduction of performance analysis tools offers valuable insights for future optimizations. The exploration of resilience needs and planned integration of MPI features will be a strategic approach to ensuring the performance optimizations and potential mechanisms for resilience of the four Plasma-PEPSC codes. As the project progresses, the investigation and reflections presented in this deliverable will serve as a reference point for optimizations.

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